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Abstract

In a previous work, we presented a selection of Artificial Intelligence for IT Operations (AIOps) works in failure management, based on the results of a systematic mapping study we previously conducted. This document provides an in-depth description of the methodology followed in our mapping study, describing and motivating our planning choices in terms of problem definition, search, selection and paper categorization. Moreover, this document describes other methodological instruments utilized in our survey paper selection, including a terminology scheme and a presentation of the evaluation metrics encountered in AIOps problems.

Abstract

In a previous work we presented a selection of Artificial Intelligence for IT Operations (AIOps) works in failure management based on the results of a systematic mapping study we previously conducted. This document provides an in-depth description of the methodology followed in our mapping study, describing and motivating our planning choices in terms of problem definition, search, selection and paper categorization. Moreover, this document describes other methodological instruments utilized in our survey paper selection, including a terminology scheme and a presentation of the evaluation metrics encountered in AIOps problems.

1 Introduction

Artificial Intelligence for IT Operations (AIOps) is the field of study investigating the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) for the improvement and enhancement of Information Technology (IT) services. AIOps relies Machine Learning, Big Data, and analytic technologies to monitor the computer infrastructure and provide proactive insights and recommendations to reduce failures, improve mean-time-to-recovery (MTTR) and allocate computing resources efficiently.

In a previous work, we have extracted and presented a selection of 92 AIOps papers related to failure management. Such papers have been obtained thanks to a systematic mapping study we planned and conducted specifically for the field of AIOps. This mapping study enabled us to obtain a significant amount of contributions (over 1000) related to AIOps, as well as allowing us to delineate trends and common problems within the field.

The purpose of this document is to provide an in-depth description of the methodology followed in our mapping study, delineating and motivating our planning choices in terms of problem definition, search, selection and paper categorization. In addition, this document describes other methodological instruments utilized in our survey, such as the survey selection policies for the final set of 92 papers, a terminology scheme and a presentation of the evaluation metrics encountered in AIOps problems.

The outline of this document is the following: Chapter 2 presents the methodology related to the systematic mapping study in AIOps, discussing planning choices (for the definition, search, selection, and mapping steps) and the final survey selection policy. Chapter 3 discusses the evaluation metrics used throughout the survey for comparison of the different AIOps approaches. Chapter 4 presents and defines the terminology convention utilized in our survey to categorize and analyze papers. Chapter 5 summarizes and concludes this document.

2 Systematic Mapping Study Methodology

2.1 Systematic Mapping Studies

A systematic mapping study has been conducted to obtain a relevant and representative literature in the field of AIOps. Systematic mapping studies (SMS) have been widely adopted in many research areas, including software engineering [1]. Differently from a systematic literature review (SLR), the ultimate goal of a systematic mapping study is to provide an overview of a specific research area, to obtain a set of related papers and to delineate trends present inside such area [2]. Relevant papers are collected via systematic search and selection techniques, while research trends are identified using paper categorization techniques according to different aspects, e.g. topic or type of contribution. We choose this instrument because we are interested in gathering

contributions for the survey and obtaining additional insights into the field, such as the distribution of works in the different subareas and the temporal evolution of trends. Systematic mapping studies have also been shown to increase the effectiveness of follow-up systematic literature reviews [1].

2.2 Planning

To plan and describe our study, we adopt the convention used in [1]. A systematic mapping study is then composed of four main steps:

- **Formulation**, i.e. express the intended goals for the study in the form of research questions (RQ). To understand the goals, it is important to investigate the relevance and motivation behind the research conducted. It is also important to clearly define the scope of investigation;
- **Search**, i.e. define strategies to obtain a sufficiently high number of papers within the scope of investigation. This comprises the selection of one or more search strategies (database search, manual search, reference search, etc.) as well as their modalities'. In the case of database search, for instance, it is required to choose the most appropriate paper databases, or to establish a keywording mechanism for queries (such as PICO [1]);
- **Selection (or screening)**, i.e. define and apply a set of criteria for identifying relevant papers inside the search result set. Inclusion and exclusion criteria typical involve (but are not limited to): the main topic or task, the language, the publication format, and the temporal and geographical provenience;
- **Data Extraction and Mapping**, i.e. gather the information required to map the selected papers in the corresponding categories. The categorization scheme can be defined during formulation or after the selection process via keywording. Finally, results of categorization are presented, ideally in a graphical form, by means of histograms or bubble plots.

In our work, however, the search and selection process are not linearly consecutive, but rather quite intertwined, due to the high dimensionality of the result set and the trial and error process followed. The next sections illustrate and motivate the choices made for this systematic mapping study in AIOps in this regard.

2.3 Formulation

The main goal of this mapping study is to identify the extent of past research in AIOps. In particular, we would like to identify a representative set of AIOps contributions, which can be grouped based on the similarity of objectives and focuses. We also wish to understand the relative distribution of publications within these categories and the temporal implications related to this distribution. Formally, we articulate the following research questions:

RQ1. What categories can be observed while classifying AIOps contributions in scientific literature?

RQ2. What is the distribution of papers in such categories?

RQ3. Which temporal trends can be observed for the field of AIOps?

In terms of scope, following the discussion done in the introduction to our survey, we express the boundaries of AIOps as the union of goals and problems in IT Operations when dealt with Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques. In our survey paper, we have expressed how different authors

interpret the AI aspect in different ways, with some of them limiting applicability to Machine Learning and Data Analytics. Moreover, defining clear boundaries for AI is itself a quite challenging and still open research problem. To circumvent this, we here adopt an extended convention, where we consider AI both data-driven approaches, such as Machine Learning and data mining, as well as goal-based approaches, such as reasoning, search and optimization approaches. However, we mostly concentrate our efforts on the first category due to its predominance and connection to AIOps goals (gain statistical insights) and methodologies (data collection/Big Data). The following schema synthesizes AI approaches considered:

- Data-driven approaches
 - Classical Machine Learning
 - Deep Learning
 - Other Probabilistic Methods
 - Graph learning/modeling
 - HMMs, BNs (with or without evidence)
- Goal-based approaches
 - Optimization
 - E.g. Evolutionary Programming
 - Search
 - E.g. Constraint Programming, Integer Programming, (Un)Informed Search techniques
 - Reasoning
 - E.g. Logic: propositional, first-order

2.4 Search and Selection

2.4.1 Selection Criteria

Conventionally, the selection process is applied on the result set obtained during search. However, due to the interconnection of the search and selection processes in this study, it is more convenient to illustrate the selection principles beforehand, so that the discussion will appear clearer when we describe our result collection strategy, composed of search and selection altogether.

In terms of inclusion criteria, we define only one relevance criterion, based on the main topic of the document. Following from our discussion on scoping (which requires AI and IT Operations) such inclusion criterion comprises two necessary conditions:

- The document references one or more AI methods. This mentions can either be part of the implementation (e.g. for a paper describing a new classification technique, or re-using an existing method), or as part of its discussion/analysis (e.g. for a survey describing Deep Learning solutions for anomaly detection). On the other hand, any mention to AI algorithms employed by others, perhaps mentioned in the related work section or as baseline comparison, but that is not strictly the focus of the document, is not considered valid;
- The document applies its concepts to some kind of IT system management. We therefore exclude papers with no specific target domain or with a target domain out of the scope of IT Operations. For reference purposes, we here present a non-exhaustive list of IT environments considered relevant and commonly mentioned in the explored papers: Cloud Computing, Web Server, Grid Computing, High Performance Computing, Cluster Computing.

In terms of exclusion criteria, we define the following as exclusion rules:

- The language of the document is not English;
- The document is not accessible online;
- The document does not belong to one of the following types: scientific article (conference paper, journal article), book, white paper;
- The main focus of the document is one of the following topics: cybersecurity, industrial process control, cyber-physical systems, and optical sensor networks.

However, for the special case of survey and review papers, we consider them relevant as long as we are proceeding with our mapping study, but we then exclude them from our final set of contributions. This is justified by the fact that these type of articles are useful to find other connected works through references, but they do not constitute novel contributions to their field.

2.4.2 Database Search

For the search process, database search represents the first and most important step, as it aims to provide the highest number of results and perform an initial screening of irrelevant papers. We perform database search in three steps: keywording, query construction and result polling.

For keywording we use the PICO (Population, Intervention, Contribution, Outcome) technique presented in [1]. We use PICO to derive a set of keywords for AI and a set of keywords for IT Operations. The keywords are listed in Table 1.

Then, following our scoping considerations, we construct queries so that they return results where both AI and IT Operations are present. In particular, we apply logic conjunction of keywords across all combinations of the two keyword sets (e.g. “logistic regression” and “cloud computing”). This helps enforcing precision in our search results. For keywords with synonyms and abbreviations, we allow all equivalent expressions via OR disjunction. We also perform general search queries, related to the topic as a whole (e.g. “AIOps”). Finally, we group some queries with common terms to reduce the number of queries.

We select three online search databases that are appropriate for the scope of investigation: IEEE Xplore [3], ACM Digital Library [4] and arXiv [5]. When the search database provides an API we query results by sending queries from the query set automatically; in the other cases we input queries and collect the results manually. For each query, if we obtain a very high number of hits, we restrict our analysis to the first 2000 results returned by the query, ranked by pertinence. We aggregate results from all searches in one large set of papers, removing duplicates and annotating for each element corresponding search metadata information (e.g. number of hits, index position in corresponding searches, etc.).

The result from this step consists of 83817 unique articles. For each returned element, we collect the following information: title, authors, year, publication venue (e.g. conference or journal, if present), type of contribution (paper, patent, book, article), number of citations (from Google Scholar [6]).

AI Keywords	IT Operations Keywords
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• (“AI” OR “artificial intelligence”)• “classification”• “clustering”• “logistic regression”	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• ((“datacenter” OR “data center”) AND “management”)• (“DevOps” OR “site reliability engineering” OR “SRE”) (“IT operations”)

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “regression” • (“DL” OR “deep learning”) • (“ML” OR “Machine Learning”) • (“inference” OR “logic” OR “reasoning”) • (“supervised” OR “unsupervised” OR “semi-supervised” OR “reinforcement”) AND (“learning”) • (“support vector machine” OR “SVM”) • (“tree” OR “tree-based” OR “trees” OR “forest”) • (“bayesian” OR “neural”) AND “network”) • (((“hidden” AND “markov”) OR (“gaussian” AND “mixture”)) AND “model”) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (“anomaly detection” OR “outlier detection”) • (“cloud computing”) • (“cloud”) • (“fault detection” OR “failure detection”) • (“fault localization” OR “failure localization”) • (“fault prediction” OR “failure prediction”) • (“fault prevention” OR “failure prevention”) • (“log” OR “logs” OR “log analysis”) • (“metrics” OR “KPI” OR “key performance indicator”) • (“remediation” OR “recovery”) • (“root-cause analysis” OR “root cause analysis”) • (“service desk automation”) • (“tracing” OR “trace” OR “traces”)
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Table 1: The two keyword sets obtained via PICO and use to perform database search.

2.4.3 Preliminary Filtering and Ranking-based Selection

In the filtering step we start improving the quality of our selection of papers. First, papers are automatically excluded based on publication venue, for those venues that are clearly irrelevant for topic reasons (e.g. meteorology). We also exclude based on the year of publication (year < 1990), as we are mostly interested in large-scale Web-based services and the application of AI in the period before the 1990s is irrelevant for chronological reasons. By doing so, we can exclude approximately 8000 elements.

Usually at this point, a full-text analysis would be performed on all the available papers to screen relevant contributions thanks to above cited selection rules. Although this last filtering step could partially reduce the considerably high dimension of the result set, it is still not feasible to perform an exhaustive selection analysis, even as simple as filtering by title. It is also impractical to attempt an automated selection by content, as there is no automatic full-text retrieval mechanism for all the databases of interests and it is not clear how to perform an efficient, high-recall, high-precision text classification analysis in absence of supervision. Therefore, before proceeding with the rest of the search and selection steps, we apply a ranking step on these intermediate results through several heuristics, so that we can prioritize investigation of more relevant papers. We apply the selection rules (exclusion and inclusion criteria) previously described in section 2.4.1 to the papers examined in ranking order.

We develop a new approach based on different ranking strategies. We base the method on the following assumption: although a considerable ratio of relevant papers can be identified by ranking and selecting top results using different relevance criteria (conference, position index in the query result set, number of hits in all queries, etc.), in this sorting scenario we also observe a long-tail distribution of relevant documents, i.e. some relevant papers appear in the last positions even after sorting with our relevance heuristics (see Figure 1). This is coherent with the known impossibility of performing exhaustive systematic literature reviews and mapping studies, as completing the long tail provides less results at the expense of a larger research effort. We assume the proportion of relevant papers in the long tail to be constant and to be comparable in

value to the observed number of relevant papers when sampled randomly from the result set. Based on this assumption, we proceed as following:

- We start screening all papers in the result set, ranked according to different relevance heuristics (e.g. number of hits in queries), and we observe the ratio of relevant papers identified over time;
- We examine the same papers in random order, and measure the same ratio;
- When the two ratios are comparable, we assert we have reached the tail of the distribution of relevant papers and stop examining and selecting new papers.

As sorting criteria, we use the number of hits in the search performed in the previous step, as well as other more complex heuristics, taking into account the index position in result sets and the number of citations. When examining a paper, we look into the full content to identify concepts related to our selection criteria previously illustrated. As done previously with search results, we

Figure 1: Estimated probability of relevance for collected papers (y-axis), as a function of the index in the result set (x-axis, in thousands), with paper arranged: a) in random order b) using a relevance heuristic based on search hits. We can observe how, thanks to the heuristic (plot b), the majority of relevant papers can be identified by examining only a small fraction of the set (the top results on the left side), while a random order this would render this unfeasible (part a).

gather relevant papers in one unique group. Using the stopping criterion previously described, we stop this selection step when we have identified 430 relevant papers.

2.5 Additional Search Techniques

The “early stopping” criterion previously described, while allowing a feasible and comprehensive selection strategy across thousands of contributions, has a natural inclination towards discarding relevant papers. We also expect other relevant papers, not present in the initial set of 83817, to be excluded because they were not identified by our database search. To cover for these limitations, we apply other search techniques in addition to database search. For these techniques, differently from the previous step, we apply our selection criteria exhaustively for each document retrieved.

2.5.1 Reference Search

For each of the 430 relevant papers identified in the previous step, we perform an analysis of the cited references. In particular, we adopt backward snowball sampling [7]: we include in our

relevant set all papers previously cited by a relevant paper whenever they fulfill the selection requirements mentioned above. By doing so, we obtain 631 relevant elements, for a total of 1061.

2.5.2 Conference Search

The advantage of reference search is to allow to identification of prominent contributions frequently mentioned by other authors. A disadvantage is the introduction of bias towards specific research groups and authors. We also observed how the backward referencing step rewards specific tasks and research fields as they are typically more cited or have a larger public. We therefore apply other search techniques to compensate for these facts. We perform a manual search by inspecting papers published in relevant conferences. These relevant conferences are identified via correlation with other relevant papers and have also been confirmed by experts in the field (see Table 2). We look at the latest editions of each conference, in an effort to compensate the sampling of dated papers performed by reference search. Five more papers are obtained with this method.

Table 2: List of conferences investigated (with corresponding years) in manual search.

Conference	Years Investigated
IEEE CLOUD	2017, 2018, 2019
IEEE Big Data	2017, 2018, 2019
IEEE Big Data and CC	2015, 2016, 2018
IEEE CCGRID	2017, 2018, 2019
ACM KDD	2017, 2018, 2019
AI and Big Data	2018, 2019

2.5.3 Iterative Search Improvement

To conclude our search, we attempt at improving our initial guess on IT Operations keywords via analysis of the available text content (text and abstract). Using our relevant paper set in a supervised fashion, we perform a statistical analysis to identify k-shingles (sets of k consecutive tokens) that highly correlate with relevance (Table 3). In particular, we measure the conditional probability of observing a relevant paper given the set of shingles present inside the available text content. We choose $k=1\dots5$. We use this shingles as keywords to construct new queries in combination with AI keywords (“AI” and “Machine Learning”). In this step we limit the collection to 20 results per query. This allows us to identify a total of 20 new relevant papers resulting from different queries. As a by-product, we also get in contact with frequently cited concepts and areas in AIOps, later useful for taxonomy and classification.

Table 3: Examples of k-shingles ranked by conditional relevance probability (total occurrences in brackets).

k=1	k=2	k=3
tpc-w, 1.00 (13)	defect prediction, 1.00 (34)	software defect prediction, 1.00 (22)
log-based, 0.92 (11)	[work]load prediction, 1.00 (32)	disk failure prediction, 1.00 (8)
sla, 0.84 (48)	software aging, 1.00 (13)	failure prediction model, 1.00 (7)
stragglers, 0.83 (10)	resource allocation, 1.00 (6)	cloud resource provisioning, 1.00 (5)
vm, 0.83 (59)	hardware failures, 0.89 (8)	automatic anomaly detection, 0.88 (7)

Figure 2: Taxonomy of AIOps as observed in the identified contributions. In the red box, the focus of the survey.

2.6 Data Extraction and Categorization

Once we have obtained the set of relevant papers for our study (counting 1086 contributions), we are able to analyze the available information to draw quantitative results and answer our research questions. This section describes the data extraction process and the analysis techniques employed to gather insights and trends for the AIOps field.

First, we classify the relevant papers according to following categorization aspects: target component, data source, AI method. Target components indicate a piece of software or hardware in an IT system that the document aims at improving or enhancing (e.g. hard drive for hard disk failure prediction). We group components in five high-level categories: code, application, hardware, network and datacenter. Data sources provide an indication of the input information of the algorithm (such as logs, metrics, or execution traces). Data sources are categorized as described in Chapter 4. AI Methods denote the actual AI algorithms employed, with similar methods aggregated in bigger classes to avoid excessive fragmentation (e.g. ‘clustering’ contains both k-means and agglomerative hierarchical clustering).

Then, we use the entire set of contributions to infer a taxonomy based on tasks and target goals. The taxonomy is depicted in Figure 2 and 3. We divide in AIOps contributions in failure management (FM, see Figure 3), the study on how to deal with undesired behavior in the delivery of IT services; and resource provisioning, the study of allocation of energetic, computational, storage and time resources for the optimal delivery of IT services. Within each of these macro-areas, we further distinguish approaches in categories based on the similarity of goals. In failure management, these categories are failure prevention, online failure prediction, failure detection, root cause analysis (RCA) and remediation. In resource provisioning, we divide contributions in resource consolidation, scheduling, power management, service composition, and workload estimation. Even these goal-based categories, however, represent wide contribution spaces where we can further distinguish approaches based on the specific task involved. Although we do not claim this scheme to be exhaustive, as new areas could emerge from future contributions, this scheme fulfills its categorization purpose of our extensive survey study covering past AIOps research. Since the focus of our survey is failure management (red box of Figure 2), we apply for this macro-area an additional subcategorization based on specific target problems, such as the online prediction of software failures (known as system failure prediction). Other examples of subcategories are checkpointing for failure prevention, or fault localization for root cause analysis (see Figure 3 below).

Figure 3: Complete Failure Management (FM) taxonomy.

2.7 Survey Selection

In our survey discussion we focus on failure management, so we select only those papers that belong to the five above-mentioned FM categories and exclude the others (like resource provisioning). Because of the variety of topics covered and the high number of contributions identified (despite the restriction to failure management), we limit our discussion to those papers that we consider more relevant and innovative from a research perspective. Using the Google Scholar citation count we collected earlier, we compute the average number of citations per year and use it as a quantitative measure for ranking contributions. This however represents for us more of an initial guess rather than an absolute criterion. Later, we intervene in the ranking process to prioritize variety and quality over repetitiveness, promoting within the same task several solutions varying in data sources, targets and AI methods. We also rebalance contributions across categories so that each task is sufficiently represented. In the end, out of 670 papers treating AI-based failure management, we have selected 92 different approaches (49 proactive, 43 reactive).

We group papers according to our empirical taxonomy and for each work we have described the AI approach, the available experimental results, the input data sources and the intended target components. We also emphasize strengths, peculiarities and limitation of each contribution. For each of these categorization schemes, each paper can be assigned to one or more categories, e.g. if a paper uses two or more AI techniques it will be assigned to each “AI method” category corresponding to a used technique. Same applies to the general taxonomy, for which the same paper can e.g. be considered as pertinent for root cause analysis and failure detection.

3 Evaluation Metrics

In our survey discussion on failure management we often reported quantitative results for the papers under investigation. This section provides an overview of the evaluation metrics employed for comparison throughout the discussion.

For regression tasks, a widely adopted metric is the Mean squared Error (MSE), defined as the average squared difference between target and predicted values:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i^N (y_i^{pred} - y_i)^2$$

A measure adopted across all classification problems (software defect prediction, root cause diagnosis, recovery, etc.) is accuracy, i.e. the ratio of classified samples assigned to the correct

class. In some contexts, however, accuracy may appear as a misleading metric to evaluate the quality of prediction. This is the case, for example, for problems with a high predominance of one class, where trivial models can be constructed to reach high accuracy by exploiting data skewness. A similar consideration applies to detection problems where the positive class, i.e. the detected failure, can appear less frequently than the negative class, while constituting the most critical aspect from an evaluation point of view. In such cases, it is common to adopt more representative measures, derived from the notion of contingency table [8]:

		<i>Predicted Class</i>	
		Positive Class	Negative Class
Real Class	Positive Class	True Positives (TP)	False Negatives (FN)
	Negative Class	False Positives (FP)	True Negatives (TN)

Using this convention, accuracy can be written as:

$$ACC = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$$

To quantify the ability of a predictor to identify positive samples correctly, the precision measure is usually employed, while to measure the ability of a detector to report true positive samples, the recall measure (also known as true positive rate or sensitivity) is used. They are defined as:

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad R = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

Moreover, the false positive rate (FPR, also called false alarm date), which identifies the proportion of wrongly reported failures, is defined as:

$$FPR = \frac{FP}{FP + TN}$$

Since precision and recall do not take into account the number of true negatives, some papers compare results in terms of true negative rate (or specificity) and recall. The true negative rate is defined as:

$$TNR = \frac{TN}{TN + FP}$$

Precision and recall can often be traded off with each other by adjusting sensitivity thresholds inside algorithms, so that an increase in precision can be obtained by reducing recall and vice versa. One possibility to evaluate both measures at the same time is to use the F1-score (or F-score/F-measure), computed as the harmonic mean of precision and recall:

$$F_1 = 2 \frac{P \cdot R}{P + R}$$

A second possibility is to use receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves, parametric line plots which describe the variation of two metrics in relation to changes in the sensitivity threshold. Precision-recall curves are possible, but it is common to plot the recall against the false positive

rate (FPR). From this type of curves the Area under the ROC curve (AUCROC) measure can be computed. A higher AUCROC score then indicates a better classifier.

4 Terminology

In our discussion we also adopt a variety of error-related words such as fault, failure and root cause. From a terminology point of view, we adopt the convention of Salfner et al. [9] for the characterization of faulty behavior. According this convention,

- *errors* are deviations from the correct system state
- *failures* are manifestations of undesired deviations in the delivery of a service
- *faults* (or root causes) are the primary causes of undesired behavior (i.e. the errors).

Moreover, we often encounter different terms related to data sources which may have an ambiguous meaning depending on the context, such as logs or traces. To be consistent in our discussion, we group the observed data sources according to this convention:

- *source code* represents any unit of software source code used as input to a prediction system, independently of the form and extension (e.g. function, file, module, class, etc.);
- *testing resources* comprise tools used to perform in- and post-release software debugging, in particular unit test suites, execution profiles or run description reports;
- *system metrics* measure various numerical quantities at the hardware, OS, software and environment level, describing resource utilization and the overall process state of the system;
- *key performance indicators (KPI)* provide information about the status of services and the associated requirements that need to be met during runtime operations. They quantitatively measure the quality of served requests with parameters such as latency, uptime, failure rate, availability, etc.;
- *network traffic* is the collection of network packets exchanged over Internet by different hosts. It includes the payload and control information such as ports, addresses, protocol standards and other parameters;
- *topology* is any information describing the spatial relations inside a working system, when used as a input;
- *incident reports* are collected with the help of service desk and internal problem management systems to identify common problems and facilitate resolution. Usually, they describe the problem with text and categorical attributes and they may be associated to a resolution team or routing sequence;
- *event logs* (or simply logs) are collections of human-interpretable printing statements describing software events occurring in runtime operations. They are typically stored as independent files and log entries (i.e. lines) are associated to a predefined format (or log key);
- *execution (distributed) traces* are hierarchical descriptions of the modules and services invoked to satisfy a user request. They are usually annotated with the service name or category and the time duration of each module (called span).

5 Conclusion

In this document, we discussed in-depth the methodology behind our mapping study conducted in AIOps. We planned our mapping study starting from considerations drawn by AIOps definitions and used them

for scoping considerations. We defined our goals formulating three research questions, regarding the categorization and temporal evolution of the AIOps field. We defined and applied different search and selection criteria, and we introduced a new ranking procedure to tackle the high dimensionality of our search problem. We identified over 1000 contributions and selected 92 of them treating failure management problems, for which we explained the selection criteria. In conclusion, we described our terminology convention for categorization and analysis of results, and presented a summary of the evaluation metrics used throughout the discussion.

6 References

- [1] K. Petersen, R. Feldt, S. Mujtaba, and M. Mattsson, “Systematic mapping studies in software engineering,” in *Proceedings of the 12th international conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software Engineering*, Italy, Jun. 2008, pp. 68–77, Accessed: Jun. 04, 2020. [Online]. Available: http://www.robertfeldt.net/publications/petersen_ease08_sysmap_studies_in_se.pdf.
- [2] B. A. Kitchenham, D. Budgen, and O. P. Brereton, “The value of mapping studies – A participant-observer case study,” Apr. 2010, doi: 10.14236/ewic/EASE2010.4.
- [3] “IEEE Xplore.” <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/Xplore/home.jsp> (accessed Jun. 08, 2020).
- [4] “ACM Digital Library.” <https://dl.acm.org/> (accessed Jun. 08, 2020).
- [5] “arXiv.org e-Print archive.” <https://arxiv.org/> (accessed Jun. 08, 2020).
- [6] “Google Scholar.” <https://scholar.google.com/> (accessed Jun. 12, 2020).
- [7] S. Jalali and C. Wohlin, “Systematic literature studies: Database searches vs. backward snowballing,” in *Proceedings of the 2012 ACM-IEEE International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering and Measurement*, Sep. 2012, pp. 29–38, doi: 10.1145/2372251.2372257.
- [8] F. Salfner and M. Malek, “Using Hidden Semi-Markov Models for Effective Online Failure Prediction,” Oct. 2007, doi: 10.1109/srds.2007.35.
- [9] F. Salfner, M. Lenk, and M. Malek, “A survey of online failure prediction methods,” *ACM Comput. Surv.*, vol. 42, no. 3, pp. 1–42, Mar. 2010, doi: 10.1145/1670679.1670680.